

Scientific Cruise Report

1. Cruise participants

Vessel: R/V Skagerak

Ports of call: Gothenburg, Sweden – Reykjavík, Iceland

Dates: July 9 – July 15, 2025 (part of FAROX25 cruise, departing from Gothenburg on the 2nd of July, 2025)

Chief Scientist: Leon Chafik, Stockholm University

Co-Chief Scientist: Fabien Roquet, Gothenburg University

Complete list of participants and their role during the RIVERS overflow cruise:

Name	Surname	Affiliated Institutions	Role
Chafik	Leon	Stockholm University	Chief Scientist on SWERVE leg
Fabien	Roquet	University of Gothenburg	Co-Chief Scientist
Semper	Stefanie	University of Bergen	Scientist
El Youncha	Anis	University of Gothenburg	Scientist
Gunnarsson	Jakob	University of Gothenburg	PhD Student
Krys	Philip	University of Gothenburg	GU Student
Hentschel	Susanna	University of Gothenburg	GU Student
Moulin	Titouan	ENS Paris Saclay	GU Student

2. Agenda of the cruise

A full CTD/LADCP section across the IFR to measure temperature, salinity, and velocity

3. Cruise summary

A total of 83 CTD casts were carried out on the SWERVE leg of FAROX25 cruise using a Sea-Bird 911 CTD and deck unit configured to measure pressure, temperature (dual sensors), conductivity (dual sensors), dissolved oxygen, beam transmission, and chlorophyll fluorescence. The CTD was mounted on a CTD-/hydrographic frame and launched with a LARS (launch and recovery system), 3 tonnes at 3 metres. The bottom approach was controlled by real time altimeter data and profiles was stopped at between 5 and 10 m from the bottom. Discrete water samples were collected using a rosette frame holding 24 10-L Niskin bottles at the bottom of a subset of stations. Calibrations of the first set of CTD sensors were performed by the manufacturer before the start of the field season. The near perfect matching between the two sets of CTD sensors, at least during the first half of the cruise, proves that the second set of CTD sensors did not suffer calibration biases.

The IFR transect followed by a 6x6 grid of closely spaced stations (minus 4 stations skipped due to bad weather) was carried out for comparison with the high-resolution satellite altimetry product SWOT. After the completion of each transect, vertical sections were constructed of Conservative Temperature, Absolute Salinity, and potential density.

We encountered issues with the ship’s ADCP (OS150) showing a speed-dependent velocity bias and strong sensitivity to heading. Despite several configuration tests and later processing with the CODAS package, the data still require calibration due to variable heading offsets.

Figure 1: IFR section (Section 5) including the SWOT grid (6a-6f).

	Section 5 (SWERVE leg)
Location	IFR
Mean lat	63.4N
# stations	55 (63-117)
Length	310 km

Grid SWOT: Section 6

Section 6a	Section 6b	Section 6c	Section 6d	Section 6e	Section 6f
119-124	130-125	131-135	142-138	143-147	154-150

4. Scientific objectives

The deep and dense overflow waters of the Nordic Seas are crucial to Earth’s climate and to the stability of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). A key part of this system, the Iceland–Faroe Ridge (IFR) overflow, remains poorly understood because it is fragmented across multiple small valleys and shows strong temporal variability. This knowledge gap limits our ability to assess how changes in the overflow may affect the AMOC and, in turn, global climate.

The RIVERS project and SWERVE cruise address this gap by focusing on the Iceland–Faroe Ridge (IFR) overflow system. The main goal is to accurately quantify the IFR overflow transport and map its detailed spatial structure – the primary objective of the cruise – and to produce a high-resolution grid for evaluation against SWOT altimetry. These efforts will help identify the sources feeding the system and develop a mechanistic understanding of the driving processes (Expected Publication 1, see below), as well as support the evaluation of SWOT altimetry and mesoscale eddy variability in the region (Expected Publication 2, see below).

Specific objectives are to: **(1)** assess the spatial structure of the IFR overflow and quantify its local sources, **(2)** investigate its relationship with mesoscale eddies and the overlying Atlantic waters, and **(3)** evaluate the capability of the SWOT satellite mission to capture these fine-scale oceanic features

5. Station/activities log

See separate excel sheet for the cruise log.

6. Data document sheet

Data and sample storage and availability

Equivalent to a scientific abstract: including authors, title, publication, date, reference, paragraph summary of cruise/aims, keywords, organisation.

7. Preliminary results

Figure 2 presents the preliminary hydrographic and velocity sections across the Iceland–Faroe Ridge from the SWERVE cruise. The temperature and salinity panels clearly show the layering between warm Atlantic Water above and the colder, denser overflow water below, with the $\sigma_\theta = 27.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ isopycnal marking the interface between them. The lower panel shows the geostrophic velocity field derived from the LADCP data, revealing strong southward (negative) flow of dense overflow water near the bottom.

These first results demonstrate the high quality and resolution of the CTD and LADCP data and provide a very (and unprecedented) detailed picture of the flow structure, especially that of the overflow. They already point to multiple, well-defined overflow branches and strong topographic steering along the ridge. Together, these findings form the foundation for Expected Publication 1, which will quantify the IFR overflow transport, describe its spatial structure, and assess the physical processes controlling its variability.

Expected publications:

1. A paper on the hydrographic and velocity structure of the Iceland–Faroe Ridge overflow based on CTD/LADCP data from the SWERVE cruise.
2. A paper focusing on the SWOT grid and its validation against SWOT satellite data and conventional altimetry.

Data repository planned for data submission as well as planned date for submission:

All data will be stored in the Bolin Centre Database once the publications are completed and published.